

Our Mythical Childhood...

The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges

**Our Mythical Events
to Celebrate the 10th Anniversary
of the European Research Council**

March 2017

ERC and Our Mythical Childhood

The European Research Council (ERC) is celebrating its 10th Anniversary. Owing to its support, within the framework of the Consolidator Grant, in 2016 we embarked on a wonderful research journey with the Project *Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges*.

The Project aims at developing a pioneering approach to the reception of Classical Antiquity understood as an important cultural experience that contributes to the formation of the young people's identities along with their initiation into adulthood. We apply regional perspectives as extremely valuable contexts of the reception of Antiquity, which is not only passively taken in, but also actively reshaped in children's and young adults' culture in response to regional and global challenges. Thus, the essence of this innovative approach consists in comparative studies of differing reception models across the continents: in Europe, America, Australia and New Zealand and – a bold but necessary step – in parts of the world not commonly associated with Graeco-Roman tradition: Africa and Asia. The shared heritage of Classical Antiquity, recently enhanced by the global influence of popular culture (movies, Internet activities, computer games inspired by the classical tradition), gives a unique opportunity – through the reception filter – to gain deeper understanding of the key social, political, and cultural transformations underway at various locations.

We deeply believe in the idea of “research for society”. Thus, we hope that the added value of this Project, carried out by an international team of scholars, will be its broad impact on the frontiers of scholarship, education, and culture, through such tasks as a comparative analysis of the school curricula worldwide, animations of ancient vases, materials on how to use ancient myths in work with autistic children, and a supra-regional database of classical references (*Our Mythical Survey*).

Our Mythical Childhood team is happy to celebrate the 10th Birthday of the ERC. On this occasion we are meeting at our institutions in March (due to the requirements of individual academic calendars and cultural and religious reasons intrinsic to this intercontinental Project, three meetings will be held in the third and fourth week of the month). The European Research Council is now growing beyond childhood. As it ventures ahead, we know that the institution's child-like curiosity and joy in exploring the world will continue to shine out! Happy Birthday, ERC!

Should you have any questions about the Project, do not hesitate to contact Prof. Katarzyna Marciniak (Principal Investigator): kamar@al.uw.edu.pl and Magdalena Gorlińska (Project Officer): maggo@al.uw.edu.pl.

University of Warsaw Poland

DATE: 15th March 2017

TIME: 10 a.m.–1.30 p.m. (Central European Time)

VENUE: Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, Dobra 72, White Villa, conference room

PARTICIPANTS: Dean and Vice-Deans of the Faculty, Warsaw team of the Project, participants in the Project’s seminar, staff and students of the Faculty, teachers and students from three invited high schools, other guests – all are very welcome!

tion that are living components of our world and – to quote the famous Horatian maxime (*docere, movere, delectare*) – a source of wisdom, commotion, and delight.

Phot. Archive of the Faculty of “Artes Liberales”

com or the PhD students involved in the Project: Dorota Bazylczyk: dorota.bazylczyk@student.uw.edu.pl and Anna Mik: anna.mik@gmail.com.

ERC Day at the Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

The meeting at the Host Institution will go beyond the borders of academia. We have invited not only scholars and the University students, but also the teachers and their students from three high schools in Warsaw and the surrounding areas as a result of our belief in the importance of a close collaboration in research and education.

In the first part of the meeting, the guests will be welcomed at the Faculty by the Dean Prof. Robert A. Sucharski and they will be introduced to the milieu of Artes Liberales. Next, the team members of the UW wing of the Project will present the ERC and the main tasks planned within the Grant. They will also discuss the very first results of the Project – the chosen examples of the reception of Classical Antiquity in children’s and young adults’ culture. In this presentation, moderated by Dr. Elżbieta Olechowska and Dr. Hanna Paulouskaya, they will be joined by the PhD students and students who are participating in the experimental Project seminar led at the Faculty by Prof. Katarzyna Marciniak – the Principal Investigator.

The second part of the meeting will be dedicated to an interactive game session. The participants in the event will have an opportunity to play Scrabble in Latin and many more famous or niche games, inspired by Classical Antiquity, in Polish language version. For example, they will have a chance to become a ‘new Homer’ and create their own myths. Thus, the participants in the event will both learn about the ERC-funded Project and discover some unexpected aspects of the reception of the ancient tradi-

Additionally: two lectures including the presentation of the ERC and the Project by Prof. Katarzyna Marciniak at the University of Bologna in the ERC Week:

- *Die Rezeption der antiken Kultur in Polen – Geschichte, Methoden und Perspektiven;*
- *Sulle tracce delle mitiche bestie – la ricezione delle creature dalla mitologia greca nella cultura contemporanea.*

Should you have any questions about the Warsaw event, do not hesitate to contact Dr. Hanna Paulouskaya: handziapa@gmail.com.

University of Roehampton United Kingdom

DATE: 16th March 2017

TIME: 5 p.m.–6.30 p.m. (Universal Time Coordinated)

VENUE: UR Adam Room in Grove House

PARTICIPANTS: London team of the Project, Faculty staff and students, other guests – all are very welcome!

ERC Day at the University of Roehampton

Over the next five years, the University of Roehampton will be part of the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project, funded by the European Research Council, to develop a pioneering approach to the role of classics as a transformation marker in children's and young adults' contemporary culture. This event, held during the 2017 ERC Week, will introduce the Roehampton wing of the Project. It will include presentations from the following academics who will introduce how their work is unfolding:

- Susan Deacy – *Autism and Classical Myth*,
- Sonya Nevin – *Vase Animations on Mythical Themes*,
- Katerina Volioti – *Gods and other Mythical Creatures in Literature for Young Children*.

You will also hear about the *Our Mythical Survey* – a database of classical mythology in children's culture which is being collected by scholars around the world.

More information:

Roehampton News: www.roehampton.ac.uk/humanities/news/funding-received-to-research-benefits-of-ancient-myths-for-children-diagnosed-with-autism-

Susan Deacy's autism blog: www.myth-autism.blogspot.co.uk

Sonya Nevin's and Steve K. Simons' animations blog: www.panoplyclassicsandanimation.blogspot.co.uk

Should you have any questions about the Roehampton event, do not hesitate to contact Dr. Susan Deacy: s.deacy@roehampton.ac.uk.

Phot. from www.classicsconfidential.co.uk

Bar-Ilan University
אוניברסיטת בר-אילן

Bar-Ilan University Israel

DATE: 22nd March 2017

TIME: 17.00 (Israel Standard Time)

VENUE: Beck Auditorium, Bar-Ilan University

PARTICIPANTS: Bar-Ilan team of the Project, staff and students of the Department, participants in the international conference on Prometheus, Pandora, Adam and Eve; other guests – all are very welcome!

ERC Day at the Department of Classical Studies at the Bar-Ilan University

The event will be incorporated in an international conference *Prometheus, Pandora, Adam and Eve: Archetypes of the Masculine and Feminine and their Reception throughout the Ages* organized by Dr. Lisa Maurice at Bar-Ilan University. The participants and guests will hear about the ERC and the Project with a special focus on the venture *Our Mythical Education* – the broad query undertaken within the framework of the Project to elaborate a supra-regional comparative study of the employment of ancient myths in school curricula across the continents. This venture, resulting in a joint publication edited by Lisa Maurice, aims to look at how ancient myths are used in education worldwide.

School texts have a lasting influence on children, as material to which they are exposed at a young age. Such an investigation will therefore both be of considerable interest and provide a great deal of information about the role of classical mythology in societies. Thus, both content and usage will fall within the context of the venture, which will investigate what texts are set, for which ages, how they are used in different ways and why. The publication will both present the results of the study and analyze them, including conclusions about how myths have been used and what implications may be drawn from such usage.

Should you have any questions about the Bar-Ilan event, do not hesitate to contact Dr. Lisa Maurice: lisa.maurice@biu.ac.il and Tikva Schein: tikva.blaukopf@gmail.com.

Phot. Archive of the Bar-Ilan University

University of New England Australia

DATE: 24th March 2017

TIME: 9.30 a.m.-4.30 p.m. (Australian Central Standard Time)

VENUE: UNE School of Arts

PARTICIPANTS: UNE team of the Project, staff and students of the University – all are very welcome!

ERC Day at the School of Arts, University of New England

The School of Arts at the University of New England is pleased to host an event to celebrate the 10th year of the European Research Council.

Over the next five years, the University will be part of the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project, funded by the European Research Council, to develop a wide-ranging, interdisciplinary approach to the role of Classical Antiquity in children's and young adults' contemporary culture.

On Friday, March 24, the event will introduce the Project to the UNE community, and bring together the researchers from around Australia who are already involved in the Project.

There will be a presentation about the European Research Council, the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project, open to the public.

The Antipodean Odyssey website, which will report on many of the findings from Australian and other Antipodean researchers, will be launched.

Researchers involved in the project come from a range of disciplinary backgrounds, including English literature, Classics, and Creative Writing. They will present their entries, as part of a general seminar on the subject of myth, children's literature, and classical reception studies.

Speakers include: Elizabeth Hale, Marguerite Johnson, Sarah Lawrence, Margaret Bromley, Miriam Riverlea, Lynnette Lounsbury, Sophie Masson.

If you have any questions, or wish to know how to participate, please contact Dr. Elizabeth Hale (ehale@une.edu.au).

Phot. by UNE student Kate Nicklin

University of Yaoundé 1 Cameroon

DATE: 27th March 2017

TIME: 10 a.m.–12 p.m. (West Africa Time)

VENUE: Campus of the École Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé 1

PARTICIPANTS: Yaoundé team of the Project, staff and students of the Department of English, École Normale Supérieure – all are very welcome!

ERC Day at the École Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé 1

The team members from Cameroon – Prof. Daniel A. Nkemeleke and Dr. Divine Che Neba – are working on the reception of ancient myths, in particular: of Cameroonian mythology, including archetypal cross-references with the Graeco-Roman heritage and the relevance of myths in young adults' education.

Due to its position in the African continent and its variety of touristic resources, Cameroon is often referred to as Africa in miniature. The country has a revered reservoir of oral tradition: myths, tales, legends, songs, chants, riddles, and prayers, etc., which are often told and/or recited to children, youths and adults at special times and events, especially in the rural areas. Audience plays a very important role in the narration of a story in Cameroon. In most cases the audience would involve even domestic animals such as dogs and cats that are always around in the evenings with families. The analyses of the reception of this tradition constitute an important aspect of the Project's interest in the use of the ancient myths in response to the challenges of the present times, especially in regard to youths growing up in a country of multicultural, complex history and with a focus on the potential of myths in building a bridge that may lead to a dialogue with other cultures, notably European.

During the ERC Day at the University of Yaoundé 1, Divine Che Neba will discuss these issues with the staff members and the students who will have also an opportunity to be introduced to the main tasks within the Project and the role of the European Research Council.

Should you have any questions about the Yaoundé event, do not hesitate to contact Prof. Daniel A. Nkemeleke: nkemelekedan@yahoo.com and Dr. Divine Che Neba: nebankiwang@yahoo.com.

The Structure of the Project

Graphic by Sonya Nevin and Steve K. Simons

Stay in Touch with Us!

ERC Website: www.erc.europa.eu

CORDIS Website: www.cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205179_en.html

Information on the Project: www.en.uw.edu.pl/11th-erc-grant

Clip about the Project: www.youtube.com/watch?v=sWMX5NuDRrU

Facebook: www.facebook.com/OurMythicalChildhood

Twitter: @OMChildhood

Instagram: @OMChildhood

YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/UC6zvu9EXsl0gK5rSvgnQseQ

Happy Birthday ERC!

Ad multos annos!

ERC Week 2017